

THE OCCURRENCE OF PERIODONTAL INFLAMMATION IN DENTAL STUDENTS OF 3-4 COURSES

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The article discusses the prevalence of periodontal diseases among 50 3rd- to 4th-year dental students studying at the Faculty of Dentistry of Samarkand State Medical University. The authors identified signs of inflammation in periodontal tissues, which is explained by the presence of dental anomalies and insufficient oral hygiene. The analysis of periodontal disease was observed in 85% of students, which explains the need for treatment and professional oral hygiene.

Introduction. Introduction. Periodontal tissue diseases are among the most common in the population, and if left untreated, they can lead to tooth loss [1.5]. The main cause of these diseases is plaque. Publications widely highlight the fact that young patients are also susceptible to these diseases. During this period of their life, they devote less time to health issues compared to education and career issues [3, 4]. Periodontal diseases are among the most common and complex pathologies in the structure of dental diseases, which have no downward trend both in Uzbekistan and abroad. The frequency of periodontal diseases among the adult population is quite high and ranges from 82%, and according to some data reaches 95-99%. In some cases, periodontal diseases occur at a young age, which is primarily due to insufficient oral hygiene, as well as the presence of dental anomalies [2].

The purpose of the study. To study the prevalence of periodontal diseases among 4th-year dental students of Samarkand State Medical University.

Materials and methods. To study the prevalence of periodontal diseases in 50 students of 3-4 courses studying at the Faculty of Dentistry of Samarkand State Medical University. The average age of the students was 21 years. During the clinical examination, the level of oral hygiene, periodontal condition, and type of bite were assessed. The results obtained during the examination were recorded in the dental record.

Results and discussion. The analysis of periodontal disease was observed in 85% of the students. Gingivitis was most common in 75% of cases, periodontitis was less common in 25% of cases. The inflammatory process of periodontal tissues with pronounced hyperemia and bleeding, but without disruption of the maxillary junction, was observed in 58% of students. This pathology of periodontal tissues is diagnosed as gingivitis. In 85% of cases, gingivitis had clinical manifestations corresponding to the catarrhal form. Hypertrophic gingivitis was reported in 15% of cases. Dental pockets were detected clinically in only 3 students in 17.85% of cases, which made it possible to diagnose periodontitis. The depth of the periodontal pocket in all the examined students did not exceed 3.5 mm, which is typical for a mild form of periodontitis. All the examined patients had periodontal pockets, were diagnosed with gingivitis, and were localized in the area of 1-2 adjacent teeth, due to the presence of overhanging edges of fillings in the interdental space. This location corresponds to localized periodontitis. Most of the examined students had deposits on their teeth. In 65% of cases, a soft plaque was mainly detected. Mineralized dental deposits were found in 35.0% of cases of supragingival and subgingival tartar in 21.52% and 15%, respectively. The conducted

medical examination showed that the majority of students, 75.26%, do not brush their teeth well or poorly, as evidenced by the large number of people with dental deposits. The number of people with a poor hygiene index is 55.24%. Malocclusion was found in 35.21% of the students. Most often, these position anomalies were found in 12.7% of the surveyed, as well as crowding of teeth in the dentition, 45.75% of cases were diagnosed.

Conclusions. A clinical examination of the dental status of 3-4-year students studying at the Faculty of Dentistry of Samarkand State Medical University was conducted and the presence of signs of inflammation in periodontal tissues was revealed, which explains the presence of dental anomalies and insufficient oral hygiene, which, in turn, explains the need for treatment and professional oral hygiene.

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